

Architectural Elegance of the Divyadesam of Madurai

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Abstract

Madurai is the second largest city in Tamil Nadu. **Koodal Azhagar Koil** is a famous Hindu temple dedicated to Lord Vishnu located in the centre of the city of Madurai. **Koodal** is another name for Madurai and **Azhaghar** means the beautiful one, in Tamil. The temple is an ancient one and very close to the famous Meenakshi Amman Temple. It is one of the 108 divyadesams the holy abodes of Vishnu. So it is known as the **Divyadesam of Madurai**. The Koodal Alagar Temple is dedicated to Lord Vishnu. There are three altars in the Koodal Alagar Temple and in all the altars Lord Vishnu resides in three different postures. The presiding deity of the temple is Lord Koodal Alagar who is Lord Vishnu in a seated posture. This is the most revered shrine of the temple. Lord Vishnu in a reclining posture is better known as Sri Ranganatha and his altar is just above the altar of Lord Koodal Alagar. Lord Vishnu in a standing pose referred to as Sri Surya Narayan Perumal adorns the temple. This temple is known for its antiquity, epigraphical importance and sculptural beauty. Float Festival, Panjaparva Purapadukal, and Parathva Nirnayamare are the famous festivals of this temple. Hence, the article speaks of the architectural elegance of the Koodal Azhagar Koil.

Keywords: Architecture, Koodal Azhagar Temple, Divyadesam, Lord Vishnu, Madurai.

Introduction

Madurai is the second largest city of Tamil Nadu and is located southwest of Tamil Nādu. The temple city of south India derived its name from the Tamil word *Marudham*. The city hence came to be known as *Madhurapuri* meaning ‘The City of Divine Nectar’. Madurai is one of the most important tourist spots in India. The city attracts a large number of tourists from within the country and abroad. About 4,100,000 tourists visited Madurai in 2017, out of which foreigners numbered 224, 000¹. **Koodal Azhagar Koil** is a famous Hindu temple dedicated to Lord Vishnu located in the centre of the city of Madurai. **Koodal** is another name for Madurai and **Azhaghar** means the beautiful one, in Tamil. The temple is an ancient one and very close to the famous Meenakshi Amman Temple. It is one of the 108 divyadesams the holy abodes of Vishnu. So it is known as the **Divyadesam of Madurai**.

Aims and Objectives

1. To trace the uniqueness of art and architecture of the Koodal Alagar Perumal Temple.
2. To point out the Fairs and Festivals of the temple.
3. To highlight the sculpture and Paintings of the temple.

Methodology

The study adopts both descriptive and analytical methods. The scholar applied mostly historical methods and field survey methods in this study.

Hypothesis

- Koodal Alagar Perumal Temple had a unique kind of architecture.

➤ The festivals of this temple attracted many people of the country.

Area of Study

Koodal Azhagar Temple is situated in Madurai. The city of Madurai and sites surrounded by the temple are taken as the area of study.

Koodal Azhagar Temple

The Koodal Alagar Temple in Madurai is an ancient temple that reflects the cultural heritage of the land in keeping with the tradition of the land. It is located at a distance of about 2 km the west of the city, the Koodal Alagar Temple is dedicated to Lord Vishnu, an important God of the Hindu pantheon. There are three altars in the Koodal Alagar Temple and in all the altars Lord Vishnu resides in three different postures. The presiding deity of the temple is Lord Koodal Alagar who is Lord Vishnu in a seated posture. This is the most revered shrine of the temple. Lord Vishnu in a reclining posture is better known as Sri Ranganatha and his altar is just above the altar of Lord Koodal Alagar. Lord Vishnu in a standing pose referred to as Sri Surya Narayan Perumal adorns the temple².

Divya Desam

A Divya Desam or Vaishnava Divya Desam is one of the 108 Vishnu and Lakshmi temples that is mentioned in the works of the Alvars. Divya means "divine" and Desam indicates "realm" (temple). Of the 108 temples, 105 are in India, one is in Nepal, and the last two are believed to be outside the earth, in Thirupparkadal and Vaikuntham. In India, they are spread over the states of Tamil Nadu (84), Kerala (11), Andhra Pradesh (2), Gujarat (1), Uttar Pradesh (4), and Uttarakhand (3). Muktinath, Saligramam is the only Divya Desam in Nepal. The Divya Desams are revered by the 12 Alvars in the Naalayira Divya Prabandham, a collection of 4,000 Tamil verses. The Divya Desams follow either Tenkalai or Vadakalai modes of worship. This is one of the 108 *Divya Desam* temples. There are a total of 108 Divya Desam or Vaishnavite Shrines in the country. But in only two of these shrines can one witness Lord Vishnu in all three postures- Standing, Sitting and Reclining. The Koodal Alagar Temple is one of those two temples to have this unique feature. The seated Lord Vishnu is locally known as Lord 'Koodal Alagar' from whom the temple derives its name. The reclining idol is more popularly known and acknowledged as 'Sri Ranganatha'. 'Sri Surya Narayan Perumal' is the name for the standing image of Lord Vishnu³.

Sri Koodal Alagar Temple one among the 108 Vaishnavite shrines, is unique as Always had performed Mangalasanam for this temple. Also, Periyalvar praised this temple in his literary work "Thiruppallandu". Attanga vimana considered the foremost among the 94 vimanas are found over the sanctum sanctorum of this temple. It is rare to see Attanga vimana in temples, which adds to the uniqueness of Sri Koodal Alagar Temple. The Epigraphical material found in the temple is testimony to the antiquity of the temple. The inscription gives details about the social, economic, and political, conditions and the donations made by various rulers during different periods, in addition to that they all know their historical importance.

Legendary Story

A Pandiyan king named *Sathyavarathan* devoted this to Koodal Azhagar and had a great belief in him. One day, when he went to worship **Koodal Azhagar**. But before going

into the temple, he washed his hands in the Kiruthmaala river, where a fish was found in his hand. He thought that the fish might be the Emperumaan Since the fish was one of the Avatars of Sri Vishnu⁴. Because of this only, the Pandiya Kings in their flags have the fish as the symbol.

Another great thing that has to be said about this temple is the great Raja Gopuram, which is very big with lots of architectural works found in it. In the first pragraram, there is a separate sannadhi for Madura Valli Naachiyaar. Meenakshi Amman, who is made up of Maragatham and remembers her, this sthala thaayar is named “Maragadha Valli”. On the Northside, a separate sannadhi for *Aandal Naachiyaar* is found⁵.

This Sthala Perumal is found in 3 thalam (Floor) (ie.) in the bottom thalam, he is found as Koodal Azhagar in Veetriruntha kolam, in the second thalam (middle one) he is found as “*Andhara Vaanathu Empiraan in Kidantha kolam* and the Upper thalam, he is found as Sooriya Narayanan in *Nindra thirukkolam*. The Perumal who is found in the bottom thalam is also called “*Viyoooga Soundararajan*” and he is the *Utsava Moorthy* of this sthalam.

Art and Architecture of Koodal Alagar Perumal Temple

Mandapas

There are Three Mandapam is in Sri Koodal Azhagar Perumal Temple. That is Artha Mandapam, Mani Mandapam and Maha Mandapam⁶.

Artha Mandapam

Artha Mandapam is supported by fourteen pillars rounding the flag mast. The pillars of the Artha Mandapam have been carved in many images. They are:

- Two Hanuman Images
- The Images of Lord Vinayaka
- The two female images holding lamps in their hands

Different types of images are carved on the rest of the other pillars of the Artha Mandapam. A notice board is depicting the history of the temple in it.

Mani Mandapam

Because of hanging bells that is called Mani Mandapam. It is seen next to the Artha Mandapam.

- The Goddess Lakshmi
- The Dancing Girl
- The Monkey
- The Swan catching the fish
- The two Swans

The Goddess Saraswathi, a female in a position of veneration is inscribed or carved at the bottom of the pillars. The pillars are painted and decorated in different colours.

Maha Mandapam

The Maha Mandapam comprising of Artha Mandapam, Mani Mandapam, Thirukkalyana Mandapam etc. Every pillar of the Maha Mandapam holds the structure of human beings, birds and animals and is also decorated with different colours of paintings.

On the entrance steps of kings Gopuram, Elephant statues made of stone is present. In the four pillars of Kodi Mandapam the status of Yazhi, stamping the elephants are present. It

is all kept in a monolithic pillar⁷. The status of the people belonging to the dynasty of the King from Vijayanagar is the model in the pillars next to the Vagana Mandapam. They are King Vasavappa Nayakkar, and Thimapa Nayakkar, in the position of welcoming us. All the 16 pillars of this mandapam are filled with infinite artworks and status.

In Sökkataan Mandapam, each pillar contains colourful status with a story. In the entrance of this Mandapam, there are two pillars in which two ladies with lamps in their hands are present. In the next pillar, the 10 avatars of lord Narayana status are present. The pillars on the way to go lord Maduravali's temple contain the artwork of the 8 Lakshmis. In the pillars opposite to it, the avatars of Krishna, Vasudevan taking him, Kamsan's attempt to kill Krishna is the make-up of Lord Kaali devi and his flying scenes. The death of Boodan Sagabaswan is also done in the form of status. The Kaswarai Mandapam of Goddess Maduravalli is made up of limestones. The music pillars of this mandapam are the peak of status. On the three streets of Aadi Veedhi, there is a round stage, and the status of the roaring lions is present. The artwork of Yazhi (Mythological Animal) is done in the southside's two pillars of the *melthalaveedi*. The artwork on the panel looks to be an example of all the traditional artworks. In all the stages of this panel, lord Sri Poovaraha Perumal is present along with Lakshmi. The top of their artwork is filled with attractive golden colours. The colouring flags with flowers act as ornaments. In the four corners, lions and culture status are done. It is done with minute artwork. In the bottom east, lord Poovarasahas – Vaami, in the south, Narasimma, in the west, Sri Lakshmi is drawn. The outside of this panel contains 8 Astadik Balargal with their mounts

Artworks

The artwork in this temple shows the talented works of the artists. In the two walls of the Raja Gopuram entrance, Sridevi Boodevi, Sameda Koodalazhar Perumal, and Sri Maduravalli Thayar, Sri Andal artworks are drawn. On the walls of administration officer Periyaalvar's Thirupallandu function is drawn as a colourful picture. On the south side of Karuda Mandapam, the way to Astanga Vimanam's steps are opposite to the walls in which "Manavaala Maamunigal Sri Saila Vaibhavam" is drawn. In this Mandapam, in the above hut to Dwarabalar, Sri Maduravalli, Koodalazhagar, Sri Aandal's status is drawn. In the walls of Aastha Mandapam, the Pandiyan king's prayers, and Periyazhvaar's Thirupallandu function are drawn. Colourful artworks are done above the temple of lord Maduravalli. In the temple of Sri Andal Temple, Thiruppavai songs, their explanations are written. In the down half of Ashtanga Vimanam, in the South Purakoshtam, East Lakshmi, West Lakshmi Narayana, and in the North outer wall, Brahma's pictures are drawn⁸. The Wall Painting on two floors above Ashtanga Vimanam of lord Koodalazhagar's temple: On the first top floor, the standing position of Suriya Narayanan's statue with the Sangu and Chakras in his two hands. And on the other hand, are in the position of wishing the people. Thirumagal is on his right side and Nilamagal is standing on his left side in the standing position. And also, there are all present near the status of Suriya Narayanan⁹.

Architecture

The sanctum sanatoriums of this temple are seen one above the other, it is unique to this temple. Convenient steps have been provided to reach the top floors. Just like the Peria

Koil tower of Tanjore, the shadows of Astanga Vimanam do not fall on the ground. The stone walls on the 3 sides of the Athittanam are full of artistic works. Sun's rays reach the sanctum sanctorum through the 7 windows in this wall. There are beautiful sculptures made of lime mortar on the Vimanam (structure over the sanctum sanctorum). On the third floor, the scenes of "Dasavatharam" (the ten Incarnations) are depicted with lime mortar sculptures around the shrine. The shrine of Goddess Thayar Maduravalli, built with granite stones and carved with sculptural works is seen here. There is an Unjal mandapam (swinging mandapam) full of artistic wooden works. A large Monolithic sculpture of Yallies is found here. Also, there are musical pillars in this temple. Sri Andaal Shrine is in the northern part of Perumal shrine¹⁰.

Colour story with status

On the 2nd top floor of Ashtanga Vimanam, Lord Shooraphadar with two hands facing south and foot facing opposite is sleeping in the Aadisheshah as the bed, in the Thirupaar Kadal. Near his foot, there are two devi's in the temple in the position of wishing the people, lord Perumal is in the position folding his hands on the right side, with his left hand stretched. On the south corners wall middle, the south outside Korma Avatar, Varaaga Avatar, Narasimha Avatar, Vamana Avatar, Parasurama Avatar, Rama Avatar, Krishna Avatar, and Kalki Avatar artworks are present. In this wall, to the bottom corner, Sri Garuda is done as an art, lord Ananda in the position of joined hands facing south side in the seating position. In the front of Sri Raapthinaadan is present along with Peerugu Maarkandeya Maga Rishi in the position of joined hands in the seated position¹¹.

Carvings

Carving is an act of using tools to shape something from a material by scraping away portions of that material. The technique can be applied to any material that is solid enough to hold a form even when pieces have been removed from it, and yet soft enough for portions to be scraped away with available tools. Carving, as a means for making stone or wooden sculptures, is distinct from methods using soft and malleable materials like clay, fruit, and melted glass, which may be shaped into the desired forms while soft and then hardens into that form. Carving tends to require much more work than methods using malleable materials. There are numerous carvings at the Koodal Alagar temple tower base, at the interior mandapam, mandap and on the surrounding of the temple. These five carvings are on the top of the temple tower basement, on the mandap and the surrounding walls there are small tiny carvings that have not belonged to the temple.

Period

The carvings that are found on the temple tower of Koodal Alagar temple belong to the A.D. 1550 period of King Vijayanagar. The first two carvings are believed to the period A.D.1151,1555-1556 of Vijayanagar King Sadhasivarayar. The remaining periods are unknown with handwriting two of them are considered to be from the 16th century and the last one was doubted to be from the 17th and 18th centuries. All these carvings describe the temple construction and sponsors.

Old Carvings on the Surrounding Walls

The carvings that are used for the construction of surrounding walls are brought up

from nearby surrounding areas small which are once constructed by small land kinds and left without maintenance. so the surrounding wall carvings are disconnected in detail. Most of the carvings belong to Shiva and Thirumal temples which belonged to the 13 and 14th centuries. Some of them are from the 12th and 11th centuries.

On the founded disconnective carvings praises but the kings and the name of secretaries are mentioned. Maravarman Sundarapandiyan and Kulasekarapandiyan are the names of the kings that are mentioned frequently. Most of the carvings are doubted to belong to Chola kings. This was because the carvings mostly consist of the name of Chola rulers. Dhatchinimandakathipathi, Amarasavitalamahadhevarayar's superior Thimavapanayar had done more for the growth of Vaishnavas. The two more carvings explain that in 1551 in Thirumegakalaperumal temple he did specially dedicated works by giving his lands under the temple control. One of the carvings explains that it was the order of the Lord Kalamega Perumal and some say it was his interest. Both of them are now in the Kudalalagiya Perumal temple. There was a carving explaining the praise of the Vijayanagar king in the basement of the Ashtanga tower of the temple. Ramarasavitala, Mahadhevaraayar's superior Thirumavapanayar "a gifted lot of villages to him". he showed his willingness with a cute smile¹².

In the Kudalalagiya Perumal temple, there was a carving showing both two people. So based on his order the areas like Perungudi, Irattaikulam, Vannanendal, Kumulangulam and the areas nearby Avaninarayanapuram, Sindamani village, Mullipallam, Thirupuvanam areas Pulvaiyekarai etc., are gifted. Among this Perungudi is near to airport and the area before it which was called Avaninarayanapuram is now named Avaniyapuram. From Narikudi to Thirupuvanam there are some areas as denoted before. From those areas, a certain fixed number of crops is given to the temple account as ordered by the king. for saving all these things a house was also allocated, for those who are following this are given the temple's special food.

Ashtanga Vimana Artha Mandapaa

Ramarashala Vitala Thever, Thimapanayakar, Immudielappanayakar during their rule kudalalagiya Perumal mandapa works were finished. But some scriptures records show that the remaining parts of Ashtanga Tower's surroundings were constructed during the 16th century of Thimavapanayakar. In the same period, the Thirumogur Kalamega Perumal temple may be constructed. It was doubted that the same man may have reconstructed the Pandiyan period Ashtanga tower into a big one from some scripture drawings¹³.

All these temples are constructed before Vijayanagar King's i.e. by Pandiyas. This is identified from the status carvings. The bronze statues indicate that they belonged to the 10th century. So, from the Pandiya period itself, these temples are maintained by Vijayanagar King's Nayaka Kings during the period 16th century. All the statues are proof of this¹⁴. The Arthamandapa before the Ashtanga tower was constructed by Kandadaikomanan for his brother. The process went on during the period 16th century Pilavanga year Puratasi month to Nana year Aani month. Kandadai Annan's name was used frequently after the king was denoted in the carvings. Kudalalagiya Perumal's inner area works were completed by Navamanikam Alangarapattar during the 16th century. Similarly, the work at Perumananallur

was completed by Alagarteiva Selai Perumal. This area was situated on the way to Thirupuvanam. This was assured by two carvings.

Natapanmaikarar Statue

In Kudalalagiya Perumal so many statues are launched. All those are having their hands joint indicating their respect for Lord Perumal in front of Navanedakrishnan Sanathi the statues indicate a person.

Important Carvings

1. Place: At temple tower's three sides except at top carvings. The description of the temple is donated under M.E.R no 558,559,1911 in Chennai.

Period: Salivaganasagapthamam, 1473(1551) on Vijayanagar king Sadaisvadevamagathayar's period (ac1542-1570)

Content: To Vijayanagar Dhatchinimandalathipathi Ramarasavitalamahadevaraayar his superior's son Thimavapanayakar due to some responsibility he gifted many small areas are described in carvings. The crops cultivated from these areas are given to temple accounts. These things are believed to be accepted by lord Thirumal. Those who are engaged in this work are honoured by giving the foods blessed by God.

2. Place: At temple tower's three sides except at top carvings. The description of the temple was denoted under M.E.R.no557/1911 in Chennai.

Period: To Vijayanagar's Dhatchinimandalathipathi Ramarasavitalamahadevaraayar period (ac1555-1556)

Content: The carvings here explain about Kudalalagiya Perumal temple beyond the 3rd period Kandadaikonaman's servings. He did it with 1600rs for his brother. Ramaratshala Vitala Dhevar Thimavapanayakar, Immudielappanayakar period it was done. In these carvings, the number of workers was also denoted.

3. Place: Kudalalagiya perumal temples inner carvings of Manimandapas right side carvings. It was not yet registered.

Period: A.C 16th century

Content: The person who made the entrance of Manimandapa named Alaghar deivaselaiperumal may have done this too.

Carved Lines:

- Andanatu Peru
- Mananallur Alagar
- Dheivaselai Perumal
- Sadaseva

4. Place: Kudalalagiya Perumal temple inner carvings of Manimandapas left side carvings. It was not yet registered.

Period: A.C. 16th century.

Content: The carving is made by Alangarpatar.

Carved Lines:

- Navamanik
- Kam Alanga
- Ra Patarsa

➤ Dhaseva

5. Place: This carving was about the things scribed at the entrance statue at Navanetha Krishnan temple. It was not yet registered.

Period: Based on A.C.17th and 18th centuries.

Content: The carvings are nearly Perumal Nayakar's son Arisikandar's carvings.

Carved Lines:

- Ruthroth, Karivarsam Thai, Uya Vu Perumal Nayakar, Kumaran Ari, Sikanda Na, Ttanmai, (Ma) Sriramajeyam, Sada (seva)

The 17th century was a great period of titanic work under the Nayaks of Madura. During this period the animal motif with fantastic detail as seen in the outstanding sculpture at Madurai temple may be seen. Though stylized, this art is full of vitality. A pair of rampant, furious horses whose heads support the pillars, are carved with great skill and vigour. The riders are shown in realistic poses trying to control them. Each sculpture is realistic though the concept is fantastic.

Festivals

An integral part of Indian culture, Indian festivals are innumerable in number and are equally varied in origin marking the national regional, local, religious, seasonal, and social fervour. Each festival is unique in style and is characterized by colour, gaiety enthusiasm, fests, and heterogeneity of prayers and rituals. Many of these festivals are common to most parts of India, though called by different names and celebrated differently in the various parts of the country. In ancient days, the Tamil communities were in the habit of conducting common festivals to celebrate with a great job in a commonplace to find unity in diversity. The same habit is also continuing nowadays in almost all parts of Tamil Nadu¹⁵. The festivals were celebrated to commemorate war victories, harvest days of food grain crops, and seasonality change. There was so much evidence to prove that various tended festivals (*Thiruvizha*) were celebrated in the ancient city of *Poombukar* of Tamil Nadu. Among the festivals celebrated "*Indira Vizha*" played a leading part in those days.

The Tamil poet "*Arnmuga Navaler*" defines, "*Thiruvizha*" as detailed below *Thiruvizha* will be conducted about ten to twelve days in a year. During that day the small "Idols of God" will be decorated grandly and they will be placed in different chariots small processing will be conducted around the temple and street in this particular town or village. Festivals offer the opportunity to bring out unity, hospitality, sincerity, equality, dignity, responsibility, popularity, charity, discipline, and hygiene, among the people. They offered chances for gathering and merry-making. Festivals even stand for the testimony of the social and religious instincts of the people. Further, the festivals are the basis of religion, philosophy and culture. As such it is a must to have an analysis of the various festivals carried out by the Madurai Sri Koodal Alzhgar Thirukkivil. Festivals are celebrated based on Tamil months¹⁶.

Festivals of Koodal Azhagar Perumal Temple

1. The Festivals of Chittirai Month

Chittirai Month is believed that it is the first month of the Tamil year. On the first day of *Chittirai* month, all the people go to this temple and offer Poojas to the primary god and goddess. It is very common in this temple. Tamil New Year special Poojas & Lord Perumal

Purapaadu were also conducted. During *Thiruvadhirai Natchatira*, the *Udayavar Thirunatchatiraa* festival will be celebrated for 10 days¹⁷.

2. Vaigasi Month

In the Tamil Month of *Vaikasi*, the temple has its annual festival. It is related to an incident record in the history of the Temple. During the month of *Vaikasi*, the twelve days festivals are celebrated. Every day the primary deity Perumal is bathed, *abhisheka* is arranged with various things such as Milk, Curd, Rose Water, and Turmeric Powder etc. Special offerings by various varieties of rice and other things are offered to the God Perumal. This Festival is arranged for hailing the Lord Vishnu, who is treated as the protector of all lives. On the Tenth day “*Ther Thiruvizha*” (Car Festival) is celebrated on Asterism of *Thiruvonam*, and the image of Perumal is taken in procession to offer darshan to devotees on the day of *Thiruvonam*¹⁸. The chariot festival has to celebrate for 14 days. On the 9th day, *Anusha Natchatira*'s “Chariot Festival” will happen. During *VisagamNammalvar mangalasaana* will be conducted.

3. Aani Month

Karudda Seva, *Sayaana* festival, *Muppalaseva* festival & *Oilkappu* festival are celebrated. On *Swathi natchatira Periyalvaar uthsava* will be celebrated for 10 days. On *Anusana Nadhamuni's mangalasaana* will happen. “*Thiru Vadipuura Natchatira Thiruvila*” will be happen for 10 days. During 7th-day “*Sayana Uthsavam*” will happen¹⁹.

4. Aadi Perukku Vizha

During the month of Aadi, the *Aadi Perukku Vizha* is celebrated. On that day Perumal offers a *darshan* (means to see) to the devotees with a graceful appearance.

5. Aavani Month

In this month the birthday Krishna is celebrated. The day after, the *Uriyadi Thiruvizha* will be conducted in the temple. On this occasion, *Thirupavithira* & *Uriyadith* festivals will be celebrated.

6. Purattasi Month

Purattasi is the special month for the *Vaishnavist* to worship the Lord Vishnu. Every Saturday of this month, Lord Perumal offers a special *darshan* to the devotees with a graceful appearance. *Navarathiri* is celebrated through the nine days of the Tamil Month of *Purattasi*. *Navarathiri* is the celebration, to get rid of darkness, ignorance and evils. It destroys the ill and replaces them with virtuous qualities. *Navarathiri* festival on no moon day, milk *abhisheka* will be done. In addition to that Five *Garuda Seva*, Four *Masi Street Purapadu* and on *Vijayadhasami* throwing arrows functions will also happen.

7. Aypassi Month

On *Diwali* for *mulavarthailakapu* and *ManavalaMamuni* festivals are celebrated for 10 days.

8. Karthigai Month

The celebration of asterism with all grandeur is done during the Tamil Month of *Karthigai*. On the day, various kinds of lights are arranged in various places of the temple. The lighting of the Bone fire on the day is an important feature. The priest circumnutates thrice and set fire to that. The burnt sticks are taken to their houses by the devotees, the

farmers keep them stuck in their fields. By that, they believed that they could reap a bumper harvest. *Thirukarthiga* and *Thirumangai AlvarThirunatchthira* festivals will be celebrated for 10 days. On *Rohini*, *Thirupanalvar Thirunatchatiria* will happen.

9. Margali Month

Vaikuntha Ekathesi, occurs on the Eleventh day of the month, Margali. It is a special festival in this temple. On that day “The Gate of Paradise” is open to all pious. Other names of the feast viz. “*Swarga Vasal*”, “*Gate of Heaven*”. It is followed as a fasting day for the devotees. It is celebrated in all Vaishnava temples in general. On the birth of the New Year, *Pagalpathu*, *Vaigunda Ahathasi* & *Irrapathu* functions will be celebrated.

10. Thai Month

During the Tamil month of Thai, the First Day of this month, Perumal with *UpayaNatchiyar*, offers *darshan* to their devotees, in front of the *Maiya* Mandapam. *KanupariVettai* functions & on the same month's first date *Thayaar*, and Perumal exchanging flowers functions will happen. During every Thai month, *Thiru Makisaialvar* & *Kurathalvar* functions will be celebrated.

11. Massi Month

Theppa Thiruvila function will be celebrated for 12 days. On *PunarvasviKulasekaralvar* function will be celebrated²⁰.

12. Panguni Month

On *Uthiram Sri MadhuravalliThayar's* marriage, *Vasanthosvam* for five days & on *Sukalapatcha Thuvadhasi Kajendra Motchana Covarthanagiri* function & *Srirama Navami* function will also be celebrated.

Float Festival at Koodal Azhagar Temple

The Float Festival (*Theppathiruvizha*) of the Koodal Azhagar Temple was conducted at the Perumal Teppam during the month of Markazhi. The boats were decorated with the statues of Koodal Alagar and taken into a procession and round around the mandapa at teppan. On the occasion of *Mahasamprokashanam*, the Koodal Alagar, Madurai is thronged by a large number of devotees. This festival was celebrated grandly in the olden days. But nowadays there is no water in this teppam.

Panjarparva Purapadukal

During the birth of Tamil New Year, *Suklaptchi Agadesi*, *KrisnapatchaAgadesi*, the full moon of *Thiruvonam* days “*Sri Viyuga Sundararajan*” will give darshan in *Pallaku*. On Addi Street, *purapadu* will happen. During *Panjarparvam* on Friday for both “*Sri Viyuga Sundararajan&Thayaar*” on the same *Sannathi*, the *Pooja* will be conducted. Arulmigu Maduravalli Thayar on *Pirathi* week in seeing *purapadu*, will give vision on Unjal. A Koodal Azhagar Perumal Temple festival is also a part and parcel of the Chitrai festival of Meenakshi Amman Temple. During the festival, Koodal Azhagar was taken into the procession and sent to Madurai Meenakshi temple and conducted the wedding ceremony of Lord Sundaeswara and Meenakshi. The float festival of Koodal Azhagar Temple is also very popular and thousands of pilgrims and devotees assemble here from all parts of Madurai.

Parathva Nirnayam

The festival of "Parathva Nirnayam" is celebrated every year by the Lord Koodal

Alagar and is taken to "Meykattum Pottal" (the site where the supremacy of the Lord, established) in the Tamil Month of Margali is a commemoration of the above-said event.

Conclusion

The Koodal Azhagar Perumal Temple at Madurai occupies an important place among the ancient temple of Tamil Nadu. This temple is not known for its antiquity but also its sculptural beauty. The Perumal temple possesses all the best characteristics of the ancient Vaishnava temple. Above all this temple in Tamil Nadu has got a couple of sanctums one for Perumal and another for Thayar. The Epigraphical material found in the temple is testimony to the antiquity of the temple. The inscription gives details about the social, economic, and political, conditions and the donations made by various rulers during different periods, in addition to that they all know their historical importance. The festivals celebrated in this temple mark a new mile in Indian culture. Inscriptions of the temple also testify to the fact the people evinced great pleasure in conducting the festivals and rituals on various holy occasions. They give scope for the confluence of different cultures. The Koodal Alagar Temple Carvings and architecture should be preserved by the Government. The Koodal Alagar Temple has two tanks. Many Madurai people don't know about these tanks. It was forgotten by many people. They are in the endangered condition in Madurai. The people of Madurai must aware of their water resources and should take protective measures. This is not only in Madurai, all over Tamil Nadu the same condition prevailed. Water scarcity is a mounting problem day by day. The present generation should take responsibility to preserve water bodies in Tamil Nadu.

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